

1

yots'enodzida

2

tsuya

3

Not'wkh.

4

Nonghit'wk.

5

ch'eyona'

6

dotron'

2

**bird (birds
of summer)**

1

drone

4

**It has
landed.**

3

It is flying.

6

raven

5

eagle

7

ełtr'eyh

8

k'och'enatt'wghenh

9

Khwnit'anh.

10

K'okhideneyh.

11

Dotron' nit'anh khw

12

Lis noghelbet.

8

pilot

7

wind

10

**They are
working.**

9

See it.

12

**It is
spinning.**

11

**Bird's
eye view**

13

ts'eba

14

ch'etth'ena' t'on tr'eł'ani

15

ch'etth'ena' t'on tr'eł'ani

16

t'egheth

17

bats

18

khwkh

14

dandelion

13

**spruce
tree**

16

**balsam poplar
(cottonwood)
tree**

15

fireweed

18

**Canada
goose**

17

seagull